

TECHNISCHE
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Data management plan (DMP)

Task-Oriented Guidance for Information Visualization Recommendation

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	04/12/2024	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) . It is publicly available under 10.5281/zenodo.14276063
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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
N/A	Not applicable
TBD	To be determined (will be updated in future version of the DMP)
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Content

INTRODUCTION	4
Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data	4
Relevant Policies and Guidelines	4
1. DATA DESCRIPTION	5
1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced	5
1b Data generation and reuse	5
2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY	6
2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation	6
2b Data quality control	6
3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING RESEARCH PROCESS	6
3a Storage and backup facilities	6
3b Data security and protection of sensitive data	6
4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS	7
4a Personal data	7
4b Intellectual property rights and ownership	7
4c Ethical issues	7
5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION	7
5a Data publication and access conditions	7
5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data	9
6. RDM RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES	9
6a RDM-roles and responsibilities	9
6b Resources	9

Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Visualization recommendation system for Task-Oriented Guidance	Source code	.js ; .json ; .svg ; .html ; .css ; .md ; ...	5 GB	no
P2	Research Paper	Standard office documents	PDF	<50 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	A comprehensive and synthetic dataset for global, regional and national greenhouse gas emissions by sector 1970-2018 with an extension to 2019	10.5281/zenodo.6483002	CC-BY-4.0	no
R2	Maddison Project Database 2023 MPD 2023	10.34894/INZBF2	CC-BY-4.0	no
R3	Single and combined effect of acute sleep restriction and mental fatigue on basketball free-throw performance	10.5281/zenodo.5742821	CC-BY-4.0	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The datasets will be used to produce an interactive visualization React app using JavaScript, React and the D3 library. A recommendation system for visualizations will also be built using the same technologies. The scripts will be hosted on a public GitHub repository. The latest version of the React app will be hosted using GitHub Pages to make it accessible and testable to the public. The React app and the datasets are used in the research process that results in the publication of a research paper.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The main researcher will handle the structure of the research data. Versioning will be made with Git and will be managed by the main researcher.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at repository level. Moreover, as this data is the product of a research paper, in-depth details about the data, the values and terms used will be provided in said paper. The paper will be accessible directly in the repository as a PDF file. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

Instructions on how to build, run and also use the React app will be provided at the repository level README file. More instructions and help can also be found directly in the React app as it will be hosted using GitHub Pages. The link to the implementation will be listed in the GitHub repository.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the main researcher in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

R2 (Maddison Project Database 2023 MPD 2023), R3 (Single and combined effect of acute sleep restriction and mental fatigue on basketball free-throw performance), R1 (A comprehensive and synthetic dataset for global, regional and national greenhouse gas emissions by sector 1970-2018 with an extension to 2019) will be stored on TUfiles: TUfiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by TU.it. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any

sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2025-06-29	GitHub	DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.14277307	GPL-3.0-or-later

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P2	Open		2025-06-29	GitHub, TU Wien Research Data	TBD	CC-BY-4.0

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com>

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Users can fetch the code from the GitHub repository using git or by downloading it as a Zip file. Potential users will not need any specific tools or software beyond standard web browsers to access and interact with the data through the React app. The application is designed to be web-based and work across commonly used browsers. Users accessing the data through the app will not require any additional software installations. Potential users who wish to modify the code of the React app will need tools such as:

- Users will need access to a code editor or Integrated Development Environment (IDE).
- Node.js and npm for dependencies and running/building the app.

All of this will be explained in more detail in a README file at repository level.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	GitHub	10 years	Members of the scientific community and the general public. The app will allow users to import their own data sets and visually analyze them. Therefore, anyone interested in the website can use it. The research paper will also be published in the TU Wien Research Data repository, making it accessible to researchers.
P2	GitHub, TU Wien Research Data	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The researcher will direct the data management process, metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

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